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European
Citizen
Science

D6.4 European Citizen Science sustainability and exploitation plan

Authors:

Paula Klattenhoff, Alexander Heichlinger

Contributors:

ECSA, SD, SfC, Ibercivis, CSIC, MfN, ZSI, UP

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Contributors	ECSA, SD, SfC, Ibercivis, CSIC, MfN, ZSI, UdP.
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Abstract	This deliverable presents the exploitation plan and business model, developed for the European Citizen Science Academy (ECS Academy) which was selected as the core element due to its strong exploitation potential . Once the ECS project ends, ECSA will take over the management and long term maintenance of the Academy for which this deliverable serves both as a practical handover document and a strategic roadmap. It defines a clear and actionable path toward establishing a sustainable, high-impact European training and learning hub for citizen science.
Keywords	Citizen science, ECS Academy, business plan, exploitation, sustainability

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Version Log

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0.3	March 2026	Alexandre Torres, Clea Montanari Carolina Doran, Alexander Heichlinger and Chrysanthi Bairaktari	Review and incorporation of suggested changes - Third draft
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List of definitions and acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
DoA	Description of Action
ECS	European Citizen Science
ECS Academy	European Citizen Science Academy
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
ILCo	Instructor-Lead Course
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LMS	Learning Management System
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MVP	Minimal Viable Product
NMC	Nordlicht Management Consultants GmbH
OTE	Optimal Technical Environment
SCORM	Sharable Content Object Reference Model
SLC	Self-Learning Course
TVL XX Stufe X	TV-L stands for Tarifvertrag für den öffentlichen Dienst der Länder (Collective Agreement for Public Service Employees of the German States), which is a pay and working conditions agreement for public sector employees in Germany. It determines salary based on pay group (Entgeltgruppe) and experience level (Erfahrungsstufe). Salaries calculated in the Business Plan are oriented on TV-L.
UPCite	Université Paris Cité

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the exploitation plan and business model, developed within Task 6.4 of the European Citizen Science (ECS) project. During this process the European Citizen Science Academy (ECS Academy) was identified as one of the key resources with exploitation potential and thus selected as the core element of the business plan presented in this deliverable.

At the end of the ECS project the coordinator, the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), will take over the management responsibility and long term maintenance of this ECS Academy. This deliverable serves both as a practical handover document and a strategic roadmap. It defines a clear and actionable path toward establishing a sustainable, high-impact European training and learning hub for citizen science –rooted in openness, professionalisation, and long-term value creation for the community.

The sections below outline in detail the strategy under which a wide range of ideas for services and revenue streams were generated, tested, and consolidated and finally translated into a structured business model and a detailed business plan.

At the heart of the proposed model stands the Optimal Technical Environment (OTE) – a scalable, integrated platform architecture that enables professional service delivery, sustainable revenue generation, and improved user experience. A minimal viable product (MVP) was also defined as a starting point towards the development of enough capacity to enable the accomplishment of the OTE.

A key outcome of all these analyses is the need of a one time investment which would ensure the timely development of the necessary internal structures (described in detail in sections 3 and 4) that would allow ECSA to operate the ECS Academy under the OTE long term through a self-sustaining model. Long-term sustainability will depend not only on this technical investment, but also on continued community engagement, dedicated coordination capacity, strategic partnerships, and ECSA's ability to secure the necessary governance and funding support (described in section 5).

The ECS Academy already provides learning opportunities to several audiences and it has proven to be a highly valued resource by the citizen science community. Under ECSA's stewardship, and with the continued support of its members and funding partners, it has the potential to become a leading European and international hub for citizen science training and capacity building both in Europe and beyond.

1. Introduction

ECS is a four year project with the aim of widening and strengthening the European citizen science community. The project builds on the extensive work of its predecessor, [EU-Citizen.Science](#) where the need to engage new authors and focus more thoroughly on inclusion and policy advocacy towards a more robust and impactful citizen science community in Europe were highlighted. Through ECS we also proposed new methodologies towards long term sustainability of project outputs through the development of a business plan.

This deliverable reports on the work performed in Task 6.4 (Exploitation plan and business model) under Work Package 6 (Communication and outreach for the global citizen science community). The main objective of this task was to design a strategy for the exploitation and long-term sustainability of selected results of the European Citizen Science project (ECS), whilst ensuring that the work of ECS remains sustained beyond the end of the project. The deliverable documents the methodology applied for this task, the steps undertaken, and the results achieved. It describes the full process from analysis to ideation and prioritisation, leading to the

selection and elaboration of a sustainable business model for the European Citizen Science Academy (ECS Academy).

The exploitable results with the highest priority and feasibility were determined to be the citizenscience.eu platform, complemented by the newly established ECS Academy. The identification of exploitable resources, selection of the Academy and the development of the business were all conducted in a participatory and inclusive manner, involving not only the official contributors/partners of the work-package, but the full consortium and network members.

Through the development of this deliverable we generated a broad spectrum of ideas – ranging from innovative service formats to diverse revenue models and scalable technical solutions. These ideas reflect the European Citizen Science Association' (ECSA) infrastructure and its capacity to secure the ECS Academy growth and legacy with the ambition to build a future-oriented, sustainable, and technically robust infrastructure that can sustain itself and serve the citizen science community in the long term.

ECSA is a non-profit organisation whose purpose is to support the citizen science community. As a membership organisation it brings together many stakeholders who want to increase the democratisation of knowledge production. Together with its members ECSA coordinates citizen science projects, performs research on citizen science, and exchanges experiences and capacity-building. Most of our activities are community led and often organised through our thematic working groups which rely on volunteers, who commit their time and expertise to activities in support of more and better citizen science. The ideas explored in this deliverable build on ECSAs assets (membership structures and creation of new working groups) as a fundamental part of long term sustainability of the ECS Academy.

This deliverable fulfils several interrelated functions:

- It provides a structured overview of the analytical foundations of the Business Plan
- It documents the evolution of potential value propositions for the business model, condensed to the ECS Academy as chosen base for the Business Plan
- It traces the development of ideas and strategic options as generated during the project for a better understanding of the technical and economical opportunities the ECS Academy brings
- It presents a deep analysis of the digital infrastructure, including an assessment of existing tools on the market and potential technical solutions for building an Optimal Technical Environment (OTE).
- It details the ideas extracted from all of this work in a handover plan from project end to ECSA

All of these components are designed towards the development of a long term self-sustaining model under which the ECS Academy would be able to deliver several services both for free and at a charge and deliver much needed training to its members and the community at large. **This environment can be swiftly achieved with a one time investment as detailed in section 4.5.2**

2. What is the ECS Academy

The business plan developed and presented in this deliverable focuses on the ECS Academy as a key exploitable resource from the ECS project. Before we describe in more detail how it was selected and how we plan to maintain it beyond the project lifetime, we provide a brief summary of what it is and what can be found in this section. In order to strengthen the European citizen science community, as stated in the project's aims, knowledge delivery and exchange is crucial for a strong and growing community. So the focus on the ECS academy here is two-fold. We have identified a resource with enough features to develop an exploitation and sustainability pathway towards a self-sustaining resource and also a much needed infrastructure in support of the communities needs.

2.1 The ECS Academy

The development of the ECS Academy was the aim of work package 4 of the ECS project. Through a series of co-creation workshops described in [D4.1 - Blueprint for the European Citizen Science Academy](#) we expanded the repository of trainings created during the [EU-citizen.science.eu project](#) and created the moodle based academy (<https://moodle.citizenscience.eu/>) we have today. Moodle is a free and open-source learning management system (LMS) used to create and deliver online courses. It provides a comprehensive platform for educators to build dynamic learning environments with features including course content management, assignment submission, quizzes and tests, discussion forums, wikis, and grade tracking. Moodle's structure allows for extensive customization through plugins, and it supports various learning activities while maintaining a focus on collaborative and interactive learning journeys. All of these features created a perfect opportunity for a learning space fitting the European citizen science community where anyone could learn how to design, implement and evaluate citizen science projects.

2.1.1 - What can we find there

The ECS Academy is embedded in the ECS platform with matching visual identity showcasing how together both represent a fundamental infrastructure for giving capacity for the future of the European citizen science community (figure 1). The ECS Academy complements all the resources found in the platform with interactive and actionable training to equip everyone with the necessary expertise.

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the user interface of the ECS platform and the ECS Academy to showcase matching visual identity.

There are currently over 30 self paced courses on the Academy classified between beginner, intermediary and expert levels. Each focuses on a different aspect related to citizen science from general concepts, evaluation

and impact assessment and ethics. We also offer a calendar function where users can add their training events to be disseminated to other Academy users. Finally, anyone can find our contact details to propose or request an instructor led course that can be tailored to a specific group. These, when not part of the ECS project, come at a cost. Details on this and other services that are still being developed are described in sections 3 to 5 as they form the basis of the business model.

The development of the ECS Academy will continue as citizen science is an ever evolving field continuously growing as the needs and challenges of our society also change. A new page is currently being developed which will connect users to other learning hubs containing trainings that supplement those of the ECS Academy, namely the COALESCE, Competence Centre for Science Communication or the REINFORCING open and responsible research and innovation platform to name a few. This ensures that those visiting the academy can find what they need whilst reinforcing coordination of other existing efforts. Furthermore, to support a close alignment with the communities needs and the resources and trainings the ECS Platform and Academy offer, a citizen science competency framework was developed (section 2.2).

2.2 The Citizen Science Competency Framework

The continuous development of the ECS Academy is closely linked to the traction and recognition of the development of the [Citizen Science Competency Framework](#) (figure 2) developed during the ECS project in partnership with one of our sister projects PATTERN. This framework highlights the different competencies needed for the field of participatory research and citizen science and is expected to become an established tool to guide the creation of learning paths, track and assess learner's progress, recognising competencies, and structuring course offerings. To develop the operationalisation of this competency framework and address implications it may have within the citizen science/participatory research community, two workshops will be carried in July 2026 as part of the ECS project, so that these implications are co-managed by the citizen science, participatory research community through discussions around implications, operationalisation and thus governance of this framework.

Figure 2: Diagram of the citizen science competency framework

3. Development of the Business plan

3.1. Identification of exploitable resources

The objective of the initial exploration phase was to get an overview of the (current) strategic positioning of the citizenscience.eu platform and the ECS project as such. To this end, NMC conducted an extensive document analysis, seven interviews with all the WP partners of T6.4 and a SWOT analysis. A list containing the analysed data, the guidelines for the interviews conducted and the interview partners can be found in annex 1 and the full SWOT can be found in annex 2.

Through this process we identified 6 exploitable targets to potentially explore (figure 3) Details about the different resources can be found in Annex 3.

Figure 3: Identified exploitable targets

The derived ideas were evaluated and rated with specific criteria (figure 4). For doing so, the following six categories were used, each of which allowed for quantification:

If a category applied to an idea, one point was awarded, if no statement could be made, zero points were given and if the category did not apply, one point was deducted. Based on this evaluation the ECS Academy and dedicated web sections for national initiatives were further explored in a Value proposition analysis in a workshop in a project meeting in July 2023.

3.2 Value Proposition Analysis

We further explored these 2 resources through a value proposition canvas (figure 5) through the following steps: (1) we identify different customer segments, (2) we understand what they do, (3) explore what challenges they face and what they wish for, (4) finally we define what service or product can be offered and how this would be creating value for potential customers (more details can be found in annex 4).

-1
 +1
 0

Evaluation of the value propositions according to their usefulness

Preliminary Evaluation

	1. ECS Academy	2. Dedicated websections for national initiatives	3. Advertising	4. Paid Content and Services on the Platform	5. Temporary and structural funding	6. Consulting for industries
An existing WP or task already deals with this topic	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
This approach is already showing first results in the current funding period.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
This approach has a high probability of being feasible.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
This business model approach creates content and interaction for the ECS platform.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
This approach is consistent with the values and goals of the consortium	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
This proposal generates sufficient income to finance the necessary staff.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Total	5	4	-2	-1	0	-2

Figure 4: Preliminary evaluation of the findings

Figure 5: Template for Value Proposition

3.2.1 Value Proposition: Dedicated Web Sections

The value proposition of offering dedicated web sections through the ECS platform focuses on two main customer groups:

- National citizen science associations that do not currently operate their own platform
- Externally funded research projects requiring outreach and dissemination channels

For national citizen science associations, a dedicated section on the ECS platform can provide substantial benefits:

- A technical infrastructure that enables advanced metadata handling and integration of project overviews
- A digital hub to grow and connect national communities
- A tool to position national CS activity within the broader European and international context

Two implementation options exist: a modular white-label version that is customisable but resource-intensive to develop, and simpler landing pages with limited configurability. Research projects, particularly those funded by the European Commission, could benefit from cost-effective, scalable solutions for fulfilling their public engagement requirements. A simplified, project-branded entry point into the platform could serve this need. A key challenge for both groups lies in the open-source nature of the platform, which may reduce willingness to pay for services unless added value and support are clearly articulated.

3.2.2. Value Proposition: ECS Academy

The ECS Academy offers a value proposition centred on professional, accessible training and capacity-building in citizen science. Its services are designed primarily for citizen science practitioners, with additional relevance for researchers, institutions, and project managers.

Core service elements include:

- Structured online courses (self-learning and instructor-led)
- Tailored and translated trainings
- Certificates and recognition for participation
- Additional options such as mentoring, coaching, and “train the trainer” formats

The ECS Academy enables practitioners to strengthen their methodological and practical skills, gain formal credentials, and contribute actively to community knowledge exchange. Researchers and institutions benefit from a clearer understanding of how to integrate citizen science into their work and how to collaborate more effectively with citizens.

Over time, the ECS Academy aims to provide an evolving learning environment, a growing catalogue of expert-led content, and new opportunities for collaboration across sectors. Paid formats allow for fair compensation of trainers and reduce reliance on volunteer labour, creating a professional and sustainable model.

3.3.3 Selection

Following the identification of two viable value propositions – (1) the development of dedicated web sections based on the ECS platform, and (2) the ECS Academy – a final selection process was required to determine

which option would be prioritised for full business plan development and implementation within the remaining duration of the ECS project. To support this decision, a survey was conducted among key partners of the consortium. A total of 11 partner organisations responded and the results were clear: 10 voted in favour of the ECS Academy, with only 1 participant in total supporting the idea of dedicated web sections (more details on the survey can be found in annex 5).

Building on this consensus, the proposal to prioritise the ECS Academy was formally approved by the ECSA Executive Board on 19 August 2024. Based on the survey results and the recommendation of Task 6.4, the Board confirmed the Academy as the central focus for the remaining development work, particularly the creation of a detailed business plan. This prioritisation marks a strategic turning point. From this point forward, all modelling, implementation planning, and sustainability considerations have been aligned with the goal of transforming the ECS Academy into a self-sustaining, scalable, and high-impact service within the European citizen science landscape.

The exploitation of dedicated web sections described in 3.2.1 won't happen during the project lifetime but it offers a viable exploitation pathway for the ECSA HQ to pursue in the future.

3.4 Potential ECS Academy services

As one of the first steps, partners involved in WP4 together with the network of trainers and educators defined potential services for the ECS Academy around which the business model was developed. These sets of services were inspired from the set of services developed with the network of educators and trainers during the development of the Blueprint to the ECS Academy (see [D4.1 Blueprint for the European Citizen Science Academy](#)).

Table 1 - List of potential services for the ECS Academy extracted from D4.1

Type or resource	Description
Basic Resources	<p>The ECS Academy provides a repository of training materials, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training resources and MOOCs • Training guides • Course syllabuses • Best practice examples • Examples of educational worksheets (Moodle-based) • Editable templates • Stories and vignettes that can be used in various training settings. • A selection of Self-learning courses
Self-Learning Courses	<p>Materials for self-paced learning, such as MOOCs or recorded videos, that users can access at their own convenience. These may include Quizzes and tests and Badges for completing MOOCs. Certification is not a necessary component of Self-Learning Courses. Trainers may decide whether it makes sense to offer certification for a Self-Learning Courses. Such certification can be offered for a fee, as the cost of creating examination models is time-consuming.</p>
Instructor-Led Courses (Online)	<p>Live seminars conducted by an instructor, which include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some form of assessment (e.g., exercises, oral contributions, or tests) • Certification as part of the course (a badge is not required).

Instructor-Led Courses	In-person seminars led by an instructor, which include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Attendance) Certification as part of the course (a badge is not required). No requirement for exercises or tests.
Content Distribution Hub for Free Courses	Provision the ECS Academy infrastructure to others so their training can be displayed on the platform. This includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Moodle platform or similar infrastructure.
Content Distribution Hub for Paid Courses	The ECS Academy provides its infrastructure for paid courses, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Moodle platform or similar infrastructure. Marketing support, access to the network and audience or access to the academy's payment infrastructure
Trainer's Portal	A dedicated portal designed for Trainers, that offers exchange and resources via forums, Moodle spaces, and mailing lists. Includes support for the development of courses or modules for a set number of hours.
Practitioner's Portal	A dedicated portal designed for Citizen Science Practitioners, providing access to resources, tools, and shared expertise.
Marketing / Network / Audience	Support for marketing efforts, access to an established network, and exposure to a wide audience. Can be offered separately if a trainer or an organisation wants to advertise their training in the academy channels.

3.5 Target groups

One of the central elements of the business model canvas is the definition of target groups. Based on the target group profiles developed during the project meeting in July 2023, and building on additional work conducted in WP4, a set of clear and differentiated target profiles for the ECS Academy was developed. While WP4 focused on defining user groups for the conceptual and pedagogical design of the Academy ([D4.1 Blueprint for the European Citizen Science Academy](#)), the profiles presented here reflect the business-relevant target groups. These form the strategic foundation for the ECS Academy's financial model, outreach strategy, and service development.

- 1. Researchers and Research Performing organisations (RPOs)** have been identified as a prime target group, since they are uniquely positioned to benefit from and contribute to citizen science initiatives. For this target group, citizen science provides a valuable avenue to enhance research by incorporating additional data, such as geographically specific information, which leads to more diverse insights, unexpected findings, and increased opportunities for academic publication, i.e. enhanced legitimacy of their respective work. Furthermore, it supports improved science communication by engaging diverse audiences and addressing challenges like data validation and standardization. By using citizen science, researchers and RPOs can build closer connections to relevant ecosystems and the communities managing them, fostering meaningful collaborations that enhance both research outcomes and societal impact.
- 2. Public Museums**, as mainly public cultural institutions, are well positioned to integrate citizen science into their mandates for public engagement and education. With their rich repositories of open-source artifacts, objects, and historical materials, museums can play a pivotal role in bridging the gap between science and

society. In addition, museums usually are responsible for substantial budget amounts, which could be earmarked for CS educational initiatives (e.g. with public schools), so as to establish a potential structural source of income for the ECS Academy.

3. **Policy Makers**, spanning local, national, regional, and international levels, play a critical role in shaping frameworks that influence societal well-being. Citizen science offers broad opportunities for this group to integrate evidence-based approaches into the policy cycle, fostering democratic values and driving social impact. Initiatives like “Science in the Parliament” in Barcelona exemplify the potential of connecting scientists with policy-makers to build effective collaborations.
4. **Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and (larger) corporations** may have a growing interest in integrating citizen science into their operations. This target group relates to citizen science in several meaningful ways: they may commission citizen science activities to enhance services, foster innovation, and promote team-building within their organisations. The data collected through such initiatives can serve as a valuable commodity, helping businesses refine their offerings or contribute to social good. For companies operating in this space, courses on **ethical data management**, particularly in a non-profit or community context, would be especially relevant and beneficial. Additionally, SMEs and corporations may be interested in sponsoring ECS Academy’s activities to align with their corporate social responsibility (CSR) goals.
5. **RFOs (Research Funding organisations)** play a pivotal role in supporting and shaping the landscape of citizen science. They are deeply involved in funding citizen science initiatives, matchmaking between stakeholders, and implementing related policies and strategies. This includes working with global frameworks like UNESCO and the Open Science Recommendations (OS Recom). RFOs are increasingly concerned with the **impact** of citizen science projects, including impact assessment, evaluation, and ensuring adherence to ethical standards.

3.6 Potential revenue streams

Following the elaboration of the potential services and target groups, in a collaborative online workshop with consortium partners, NMC defined an initial list of potential payment models and revenue streams.

Single usage

One-time access to specific services or resources without requiring membership. It is designed for individuals or organisations seeking ad-hoc access and requires single usage payment.

- **Basic Resources:** Free and available to all users.
- **Self-Learning Courses:** Accessible with a single-use payment, price(s) depending on course scope, length, quality, and materials.
- **Instructor-Led Online Courses:** Accessible with a single-use payment, price(s) depending on the course duration (e.g., half-day, full-day, multi-day), level of engagement, materials.
- **Instructor-Led In-Person Courses:** Accessible with a single-use payment, price(s) depending on course duration, location, methodology and additional costs (e.g., materials, catering).
- **Other Services:** Not available (e.g., Content Distribution Hub, Trainer's Portal, Practitioner's Portal).

Basic organisational and individual membership (Current system): Members retain their existing benefits and are invited to upgrade to an Active Membership, which is the membership level granting access to extra ECS Academy services. In this membership user have access to:

Basic Resources: Free and available to all users.
Self-Learning Courses: Accessible with an additional fee.
Instructor-Led Online Courses: additional fee.
Instructor-Led In-Person Courses: additional fee.

Content Distribution Hub: Not available.
Trainer's Portal: Not available.
Practitioner's Portal: Not available.

Academy-integrated organisational membership

Academy-integrated Organisational membership

Grants access to the ECS Academy for multiple users within the organisation. The number of users determines the price of the membership.
Basic resources: Free and available to all users.
Self-learning courses: Included.
Instructor-led online courses: Members discounts
Instructor-led in-Person courses: Members discounts
Content Distribution Hub: Accessible through a revenue-based payment model.
Trainer's & practitioner portal: Not available.

Offers discounts for the organisation's members without providing direct login access.
Basic resources: Free and available to all users.
Self-learning Courses: Discounts available for members.
Instructor-led online courses: Discounts available for members.
Instructor-led in-person courses: Discounts available for members.
content distribution hub: Accessible through a revenue-based payment model.
Trainer's & practitioner portal: Not available.

Academy-integrated individual membership

Basic resources: Free and available to all users.
Self-learning courses: Included.
Instructor-led online & in person courses: Payable.

Content distribution hub: Not available.
Trainer's & practitioner portal: Not available.

Trainers benefits

Tailored for trainers, this membership provides access to specialized tools, resources, and course development support. Trainers also benefit from the exchange of knowledge through forums, Moodle spaces, and mailing lists. The exact scope and eligibility criteria for this benefit remain to be defined.

- **Content distribution hub:** Accessible through a revenue-based payment model.
- **Trainer's Portal:** Full access, including tools, forums, Moodle spaces, mailing lists, and limited development support hours (extra hours are payable).
- **Practitioner's portal:** Not available.

Practitioner's benefits

Designed for practitioners, this membership offers access to specialized resources, shared expertise, and support in leveraging tools and methods for professional development. The exact scope and eligibility criteria for this benefit remain to be defined.

- **Content distribution hub:** Accessible through a revenue-based payment model (up to 50%).
- **Trainer's portal:** Not available.
- **Practitioner's portal:** Full access, including tools, shared expertise, and professional development support

The current membership model serves an important function in maintaining open access to the Academy’s basic resources whilst also encouraging members to register and log in, which allows the ECS Academy to maintain contact, provide ongoing communication, assess learners’ progress and build long-term relationships. Based on this the business plan will therefore focus on two core revenue streams:

Single usage services. This includes one-time payments for Instructor-led courses (online and in-person). These offerings serve as a gateway into the Academy: users who participate on a single-use basis experience the quality of the training and are naturally encouraged to upgrade to a paid membership. Single usage is thus both a revenue generator and a recruitment instrument.

Academy-integrated individual and organisational memberships. As later detailed in section 4.2. Reformed membership models, the paid individual membership tiers (Basic, Silver, Gold) is the most stable and scalable source of revenue. They offer a predictable income stream and support the Academy’s long-term planning. Importantly, they also deepen users’ engagement with the Academy and incentivise recurrent participation in training activities.

3.7 Requirements

The sustainability of the ECS Academy depends on the existence of a reliable infrastructure that supports the identified functionalities, integrates seamlessly with organisational processes, offers learners a professional and accessible user experience whilst maintaining organisational manual labour as low as possible.

This section begins with the identification of functionalities and features that the Academy could provide, followed by an exploration of different tool types available on the market that support these functionalities. Based on this, we compiled a requirement catalogue that allowed for structured evaluation.

3.7.1 Functionalities and features

The starting point for selecting the right technical environment for the ECS Academy was to agree on the functionalities that the platform must provide. In a series of collaborative workshops with UP, Ibercivis, and ECSA, NMC developed a shared understanding of what the ECS Academy should be able to do from the perspective of learners, trainers, administrators, and partner organisations. These high-level functionalities were then enriched with specific features that describe concrete system capabilities.

The features were then evaluated and prioritized according to their relevance for the academy’s objectives. The prioritization distinguished between features that are indispensable (“Must” = 1.0), desirable but not critical (“Nice to have” = 0.6), features that could be covered by an external provider (0.4) which means there is no need for the tool to integrate that feature but for the team to find a technical solution for it, and features that were considered optional (0.3) or unnecessary (0.0). The following table (table 2) summarizes all identified functionalities, their related features, and the agreed prioritization:

Table 2: Prioritization of Functionalities and Features for the IT Infrastructure

Functionality	Feature	Priority	Value
Course Management	Create course	Must	1.0
	Provide skill assessments and quizzes	Must	1.0
	Automatically provide badge when a Self Learning Course has been completed	External provider possible	0.4

Functionality	Feature	Priority	Value
	Track the learners progress	Must	1.0
	Feedback from learners to the courses	External provider possible	0.4
Content Hosting	Centralized learning material repository	Optional	0.3
	Hosting of basic free resources/Webinars/Videos	External provider possible	0.4
Live Communication	Session recording	External provider possible	0.4
	Video call	Optional	0.3
Login	Login for single users	Must	1.0
	Login for organisational members	Must	1.0
CRM (Customer Relationship Management)	Manage membership levels	Must	1.0
	Manage membership payments / invoices	Must	1.0
	GDPR compliance	Must	1.0
Payment System	Integration with payment gateways (e.g., PayPal)	Must	1.0
	Multi-currency support	Nice to have	0.6
	Promo codes for organisational discounts	Nice to have	0.6
	Recurring payments	Nice to have	0.6
	One-time payments	Must	1.0
	Discount rates (dynamic pricing models)	Nice to have	0.6
Trainers Portal	Keep track of amount of consulting hours trainers get	Optional	0.3
Practitioners Portal	Exchange of resources	Nice to have	0.6
	Communication / Forum / Messenger Group / Mailing List	Nice to have	0.6
Content Licensing	Content licensing (open access or fee-based), course copyright management	Must	1.0
General Communication	Multilingual support	Must	1.0
	Newsletter / Mailing List Server	Must	1.0
	Link to the ECS Platform	Must	1.0
	Mailing lists for announcements and reaching clients	Must	1.0
	Social media outreach	Nice to have	0.6
	SEO configuration	Nice to have	0.6

Functionality	Feature	Priority	Value
	Design System for announcements	Nice to have	0.6
	Newsletter	Must	1.0
	Monitoring/advertisement of training ongoing from the community	Nice to have	0.6
	Integrate material from other platforms (marketplace)	Optional	0.3
	Download of content should be possible	Must	1.0
	General information for learners / FAQ / Help Service	Must	1.0
	Analytics (courses, learners assessment, payment, etc.)	Must	1.0
	Marketplace – offering and registering to training opportunities	Optional	0.3
Support	Support for learners / live support / trouble shooting	Must	1.0
Payment Flexibility	Paying in rates (via a subservice)	Nice to have	0.6
	Monthly and yearly membership payment	Must	1.0
Governance	User permissions according to governance	Must	1.0

3.7.2 Tool Types

After defining the required functionalities and features, the next step was to identify different types of tools that could provide an appropriate learning environment. Broadly, two categories emerged: open-source learning environments and proprietary course platforms.

Open-source learning environments, such as Moodle or Open Learn Create, provide maximum flexibility in configuring the system. They allow institutions to tailor the platform to their needs and support open standards such as SCORM (Sharable Content Object Reference Model), which makes it possible to transfer courses between different systems. However, this freedom comes with the costs of technical complexity, higher demands on maintenance, and the need for dedicated support capacities.

In contrast, **proprietary course platforms** offer ready-made environments that are easier to implement and require less technical management. Examples include marketplace-based solutions such as Coursera or Udemy, subscription-based services with annual fees like Teachable, or CRM (Customer Relationship Management) focused platforms such as Thinkific and LearnWorlds. These platforms can provide an attractive shortcut to launching an academy, but they also involve binding commitments to proprietary course-formats. This creates a potential lock-in situation: existing and future courses may have to be recreated in formats that cannot easily be transferred to other systems.

This exploration raised a number of strategic questions for the ECS Academy:

- Should one opt for full technical freedom, full potential for all specific requirements at the cost of greater complexity, or rely on ready-made systems with less flexibility and less specific features?
- Should one accept the limitations of proprietary formats, or prioritize systems that ensure interoperability across platforms?

- Should the Academy pursue a marketplace model, with limited control over learners, or a CRM-integrated model that ensures stronger control of learner data and membership management?

The latter question is particularly relevant for the relationship between the ECS Academy and ECSA's overall IT-strategy. If ECSA develops its own CRM for managing memberships, this system could be integrated with the Academy. Memberships and the number of included courses could then be directly connected to the course management and learner profiles, ensuring a seamless experience across platforms. This would allow the creation of a tailored environment fitting ECSAs infrastructure and the communities needs.

3.7.4. Requirement Catalogue

In order to move from a broad market exploration to concrete decision-making, we structured our assessment of different tool types along a condensed set of evaluation criteria. The aim was not only to describe the tools in abstract terms, but to make them comparable against the academy's requirements and analyze the advantages and limitations of each tool type systematically.

The following table summarizes the criteria we applied and the corresponding measurement scales used to assess each tool type:

Table 3: Criteria and Measurement Scale for Assessment of Tool Types

Criteria	Measurement Scale
Format	Proprietary Course Format / SCORM Format
Readiness	Fixed Ready System / Open Toolbox / Technical Freedom with Maintenance Requirements
Maintenance	Work carried out by the provider / Work carried out by ECSA
Content Hosting	Integrated Material Repository / External Repository / No Hosting
Booking System	Yes / No / Can be integrated

Based on this structured comparison, it quickly became evident that none of the external solutions could fully meet the academy's needs without creating a high risk of dependency on proprietary formats. At the same time, the ECS Academy was already fully functional on Moodle as its central platform. For this reason, the most promising strategy was to focus on optimizing the existing Moodle environment. This included testing and evaluating different plugins to extend its functionality, ensuring that the required features could be implemented in a flexible and cost-effective way.

This decision reduced the risks of vendor lock-in, built on existing user familiarity, and allowed us to align technical development with the ECS Academy's long-term governance and membership management strategy.

Research and Testing of Tools

After defining the relevant tool types and consolidating the ECS Academy's technical and functional requirements, the technical experts from Ibercivis and ECSA initiated a structured and systematic exploration of Moodle's plugin ecosystem. To ensure consistency and comparability, the experts established a dedicated test environment that mirrored a realistic server configuration. Over a two-week evaluation period, candidate plugins were installed, configured, and tested against the ECS Academy's requirement catalogue. This process

combined practical experimentation with a review of technical documentation, development activity, and compatibility with moodle's core architecture:

- **Ease of installation and configuration**, ensuring that plugins could be deployed and managed within a standard Moodle environment without extensive customisation.
- **Documentation quality and community support**, used as indicators of sustainability, future maintenance, and responsiveness to issues.
- **Functional coverage**, particularly in areas such as course management, enrolment logic, membership handling, payment processing, certification workflows, learner tracking and analytics, all of which are central components of the ECS Academy's service model.
- **Security and compliance**, with special attention to GDPR-relevant aspects, data flows, and reliance on external services.
- **Scalability and maintainability**, assessing whether plugins could support growth in user numbers, course volume and multilingual delivery, as well as their compatibility with Moodle's update cycle.
- **Integration potential**, including the ability to connect with third-party systems such as payment gateways, CRM-like features or other tools relevant to the ECS Academy's business and service model.

Within this framework, several plugins widely used in the moodle community were examined in depth to assess whether they could provide the functionalities required by the ECS Academy.

Arlo: Arlo initially presented itself as a strong candidate due to its direct integration with Moodle and its focus on training management. It offers a number of advanced features, including a built-in CRM component, membership levels, payment handling, and support for membership renewals. However, the testing process highlighted important limitations. Arlo introduced a level of complexity that made system administration considerably more demanding. In addition, its operational model aligned poorly with the ECS Academy's requirement to support both free and paid courses within the same ecosystem. This limitation was particularly relevant for free MOOCs, where simple and immediate enrolment is essential. While Arlo is a robust tool, its cost structure, added complexity and workflow constraints made it unsuitable for the ECS Academy's mixed service model

Edwiser Bridge with WooCommerce extensions: The combination of Edwiser Bridge, WordPress and several WooCommerce extensions (including Subscriptions and Memberships) was tested as a flexible alternative capable of managing payments, subscriptions and membership access. In theory, this ecosystem offered significant versatility and a mature e-commerce engine. In practice, however, the testing revealed several drawbacks. The solution required operating and synchronising two different platforms, which increased administrative workload and created multiple points of failure. Maintaining alignment between WordPress and Moodle, especially during updates or when synchronising enrolments, proved demanding and conflicted with the ECS Academy's objective of maintaining a streamlined, Moodle-centred technical environment. The architecture also added unnecessary complexity for long-term maintenance, making it difficult to adopt as a sustainable solution for the ECS Academy.

Course Merchant: Course Merchant was analysed for its potential to handle course-related transactions, especially certification and paid enrolments. The approach performed well in isolated scenarios, such as issuing certificates after course completion or managing standard payment flows. Nevertheless, it lacked essential functionality for membership management and did not provide the CRM-type features required for supporting diverse learner pathways or institutional users. As a result, it could not meet the ECS Academy's broader requirements and was unsuitable as a standalone option.

Taken together, the results of the testing phase demonstrated clearly that a plugin-based strategy could not provide a sustainable path forward for the ECS Academy. While individual plugins were able to address specific functionalities, none offered the integrated, reliable and scalable foundation required for the ECS Academy's

full service model. Moreover, attempts to combine multiple plugins increased technical complexity, created long-term maintenance risks, and raised concerns about compatibility with future Moodle versions.

In light of these findings, the technical teams from Ibercivis and ECSA concluded that relying solely on existing plugins would not allow the ECS Academy to operate effectively or to expand in line with its strategic vision. A more coherent and future-proof approach is needed, based on the development of a custom technical environment within Moodle that brings together selected functionalities in a stable and unified way.

The results of the testing of plugins led to a decisive conclusion: in order to align the ECS Academy’s technical infrastructure with its business model, ECSA would need to develop its own technical environment within Moodle. This environment would integrate a carefully selected set of functionalities and features and extend Moodle beyond its standard capabilities. This led to the development of 2 plans, an Optimal Technical Environment (OTE), representing the fully developed configuration in which all identified requirements are covered within Moodle and a Minimal Viable Product (MVP) which captures the most critical functionalities necessary for the ECS Academy to function, while postponing advanced features and deeper integrations to a later stage. This pragmatic step ensures that the ECS Academy can already offer a coherent learning experience, while keeping the path open toward a more comprehensive technical environment once the necessary investment becomes available. The table below (Table 4) summarises what each plan includes:

Table 4 - Description of the MVP and the OTE.

Potential plans for the future of the ECS Academy	
MVP	OTE
<p>The MVP consists of the existing platform and the associated Moodle system and is characterised by the following features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manual creation of calendar entries • course announcements, and registration forms • Manual communication management with participants • Manual bookkeeping and financial tracking • No seamless integration with the membership system; only single-payment courses can currently be offered • Number of courses limited by the capacity of those in ECSA coordinating the ECA Academy • We estimate 3–5 instructor-led courses can be delivered per year 	<p>The OTE consists of an advanced technical infrastructure and has the following features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automated integration of calendar, marketing, and registration processes • Seamless connection between registration, payment, and bookkeeping • Multi-payment tool supporting global inclusion and flexibility • Full integration of the membership system with automatic application of discounts • Learner profiles connected to learning progress with automated unlocking of higher-level courses within the capacity framework • Scalable course offering without additional administrative staffing costs • A significantly larger and more flexible course offer can be supported, depending on trainer availability and demand

The Minimal Viable Product, while functional as an initial operational setup, has several limitations: Its scalability is restricted, as the number of courses offered remains tied to individual capacity and many processes are managed manually. This results in a high administrative workload, which diverts resources from content development and prevents efficient use of available capacity. At the same time, the MVP faces a

revenue ceiling: the limited number of paid courses possible leaves little opportunity to move towards financial self-sustainability.

To overcome these limitations, the development of advanced technical infrastructure is necessary. An estimated initial investment of approximately €200,000 would provide a strong foundation for developing the OTE and moving the Academy towards a more scalable and sustainable operating model.

It is estimated that investment costs to set-up and kick-off the OTE is approximately €200,000 (see further details in section 4.4 Business Plan Calculation). This “Optimal Technical Environment” represents the foundation for a self-sustaining structure and provides a wide range of benefits. It allows the ECS Academy to significantly expand its course offering and thereby extend the outreach of citizen science. At the same time, it supports the generation of substantial revenues and contributes to long-term stability within a mixed funding model.

Membership formats will also be strengthened: attractive membership packages with included courses create a strong incentive to join ECSA, enhancing long-term engagement with individuals and organisations alike.

Finally, the optimally designed technical environment will lead to a significantly enhanced user experience: streamlined processes for registration, payment, and communication reduce risks of errors, improve participant satisfaction, and can serve as a blueprint for other educational initiatives in Europe that aim to secure their sustainability but lack the means to develop a complex technical system on their own.

4 The Business Plan

The developed business plan shall demonstrate how the ECS Academy can move beyond initial project funding and evolve into a more financially sustainable structure that preserves and expands its results in the long term. To achieve this, the plan is based on detailed calculations that translate strategic decisions into measurable revenues, costs, and investment requirements.

This business plan is not designed as a commercial strategy, but rather as a guiding instrument that clarifies the strategic orientation, identifies viable paths towards financial and organisational sustainability, and sets boundaries for what is feasible and appropriate given the ECS Academy’s public and non-profit character. Building on these foundations, the subsequent sections elaborate the underlying business model and explore potential revenue and partnership options in more detail.

The **business plan** builds on 3 pillars:

- the establishment of a reformed membership model, subject to approval by the ECSA Annual General Assembly,
- revenues from single-payment courses, and
- an advanced technical environment enabling scalability and integration.

4.1 Assumptions

Every business plan is built on a set of assumptions that provide the framework for financial calculations and projections. These assumptions make expectations explicit, ensure transparency, and allow adjustments if real developments diverge from initial estimates. In the case of the ECS Academy, assumptions were defined for both instructor-led courses and membership structures.

Instructor led courses

Courses are offered online and typically last four hours. The preparation and administration of a course requires approximately eight hours for the first delivery and six hours for each repeated delivery. A lecturer's fee of €600 is foreseen per delivery. On the revenue side, based on similar experiences, an average participant fee of €200 is assumed, which may be subject to variations depending on the market (European country) and/or target group. With an average group size of ten participants, this provides a reliable calculation basis. For modeling price variations, an average discounted price of 50 percent is included, reflecting the reduced rates granted to certain participants or organisations, being active members.

Self-learning courses (SLC) are treated as part of the fixed costs, since they do not require trainer salaries and are covered by membership contributions. They therefore do not directly affect variable costs and revenues.

Memberships

The business plan assumes two membership categories: individual memberships and organisational memberships both with discounted options in different services in the ECS Academy. Discounts are considered a structural backbone of the model and will be granted based on criteria that are still to be developed by ECSA. For example, discounted organisational memberships may be granted to non-profits or small companies, discounted individual memberships may be granted to citizen science practitioners, individuals from low-income countries, early-career researchers and students.

The following principles apply:

- **Discount Factors:** Individual members will get a reduction of the regular price by 50%. Organisational discounts reduce the regular price by 25%, meaning that discounted organisations pay 75% of the full price.
- **Cost Allocation:** The costs of a membership are calculated as one-tenth of the trainer's costs for the number of instructor-led courses included in that membership. This ensures that membership fees are proportionate to the actual teaching capacity required.

These assumptions form the backbone of the financial model. They enable the ECS Academy to combine inclusivity with financial sustainability, ensuring that both individuals and organisations with limited resources can participate, while safeguarding a predictable revenue base.

4.2 Reformed Membership model

The objective of a reformed membership model is to establish an attractive and viable model that combines the existing ECSA membership with integrated services from the ECS Academy. In the future, ECSA members could automatically benefit from ECS Academy services as part of their academy integrated membership and could be entitled to a certain number of courses per year. Different tiers (e.g. Basic, Silver, Gold) are foreseen, each

providing a different level of access. The higher the membership tier, the greater the integration of ECS Academy services (and other potential benefits identified by ECSA in the meantime. **This reform requires approval at a General Assembly of ECSA members.**

As ECSA's membership fees have remained unchanged for several years, it may be appropriate to review the fee structure in light of current costs, the evolving service offer, and ECSA's long term sustainability goals. At the same time, a system of discounted memberships will ensure continued affordability for individuals or organisations with limited resources. A number of KPIs are defined in the area of memberships that focus on attracting new members, thereby securing fair, stable and predictable revenues, while beginning with the existing ECSA members, who would be invited to transition into the proposed new membership structure. It can be expected that some current members will not continue, while at the same time new members will be acquired in this transition process. During the first two years, it will be anticipated a strong growth in new memberships. From the third year onwards, however, the growth rate is expected to slow down towards a steady yearly increase.

Building on the assumptions described in the previous section, the ECS Academy's membership structure translates the financial and strategic principles into a concrete model. The model is designed around two membership categories—individuals and organisations—each of which is offered in three tiers: Basic, Silver, and Gold. This tiered approach ensures scalability and allows both learners and institutions to select the level of engagement that best matches their needs.

Individual Memberships: The individual pathway is designed to accompany learners from their first engagement with the ECS Academy to a more committed level of participation. Non-registered users can access free resources and a limited selection of self-learning courses. Registration without a membership unlocks additional functionality such as learner progress tracking. Membership tiers then gradually extend this access: Basic covers all self-learning courses, Silver includes one instructor-led course online (ILCo), and Gold expands access to three ILCo. The pricing logic reflects the proportional inclusion of training costs while offering discounted versions to maintain inclusivity.

Organisational Memberships: Organisational memberships enable institutions to integrate the ECS Academy services into their own learning structures and make it attractive to a larger group of individuals from the same organisation. The Basic tier provides the ability to offer discounted Basic accounts to organisational members. Silver includes three individual accounts with one ILCo entitlements, while Gold expands this to ten. Beyond the standard packages, the model allows for flexible negotiation of larger bundles, ensuring that organisations of different sizes can be served appropriately.

Table 5: Types of Memberships

Category	Level	Benefits Included	Price (Regular)	Price (Discounted)
Individuals	Non-registered	Free resources, selected self-learning courses (SLC)	€ 0	
	Registered (no membership)	As above + learner progress tracking	€ 0	
	Basic	All self-learning courses (SLC)	€ 50	€ 25
	Silver	1 Instructor-Led Course (ILCo) + all SLC	€ 200	€ 100
	Gold	3 Instructor-Led Courses (ILCo) + all SLC	€ 520	€ 260
Organisations	Basic	Right to provide discounted Basic Individual Accounts to members	€ 200	€ 150

Category	Level	Benefits Included	Price (Regular)	Price (Discounted)
	Silver	3 Individual Accounts, each incl. 1 ILCo	€ 540	€ 405
	Gold	10 Individual Accounts, each incl. 1 ILCo	€ 1800	€ 1350

This structure builds directly on the ECS Academy’s financial assumptions and provides a clear framework for revenue development while maintaining inclusivity through the systematic use of discounted options. Once adopted, all existing members would be informed and given the opportunity to provide input on the plan. As a membership organisation, future steps would be decided collaboratively and with the needs and motivations of the community in mind. Though this will likely be a time consuming process it will ensure higher uptake as is the case with any co-created resource.

4.2.1 - KPIs for memberships

Key performance indicators (KPIs) were defined, that describe the projected development of membership numbers over the first four years. These KPIs establish both a target scenario and a monitoring framework, against which the ECS Academy’s progress can be measured. The table below (table 6) summarises the expected evolution of individual and organisational memberships across all tiers calculated based on a starting point of 260 (this was the case at time of this calculation in October 2025). The calculation is based on the assumption that existing ECSA members will be transferred into the new structure at the starting point (Year 0). New members are added annually, with growth concentrated in the first two years. From Year 3 onwards, growth slows down, reflecting the fact that the market of potential members is finite and will gradually approach a saturation point.

Table 6: KPIs for Memberships (Years 1-4)

Membership Type	Year number								
	0 after transfer	1 New	1 Sum	2 New	2 Sum	3 New	3 Sum	4 New	4 Sum
Individual Basic (current model)	65	10	75	10	85	5	90	5	95
Individual Silver	-	5	5	5	10	2	12	2	14
Individual Gold	-	5	5	5	10	2	12	2	14
Individual Discounted Basic	25	10	35	10	45	5	50	5	55
Individual Discounted Silver	-	5	5	5	10	2	12	2	14
Individual Discounted Gold	-	5	5	5	10	2	12	2	14
Sum of Individual Members	90		130		170		188		206
Organisational Basic (current model)	15	10	25	10	35	5	40	5	45
Organisational Silver	-	5	5	5	10	2	12	2	14

Organisational Gold	-	5	5	5	10	2	12	2	14
Organisational Discounted Basic	120	10	130	10	140	5	145	5	150
Organisational Discounted Silver	-	5	5	5	10	3	13	3	16
Organisational Discounted Gold	-	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
→Sum of Organisational Members	135		170		205		222		239
Total of ECSA Members	225		300		375		410		445

The model differentiates between individual and organisational memberships, as well as between regular and discounted options. Several key observations emerge from this KPI framework:

Early growth, later stabilisation: The strongest growth is expected in Years 1 and 2, when the reformed membership model is first introduced and marketed actively. From Year 3 onwards, the growth rate is projected to decline as the membership base stabilises.

Balance of membership Types: Both individual and organisational memberships contribute significantly to overall numbers. Organisational memberships, particularly in their discounted forms, are expected to be an important driver of scale, as they enable the ECS Academy to reach groups of learners through institutions.

Role of discounts: Discounted memberships represent not only a mechanism for inclusivity but also a realistic assumption in projecting market uptake. Their presence in the KPIs ensures that revenue expectations are not overstated and that the model accounts for different levels of purchasing power.

Strategic transition: The transfer of existing ECSA members into the new structure is a critical milestone. While some attrition is anticipated during this transition, the KPIs assume that overall numbers will rise steadily as the ECS Academy becomes more attractive through its integrated services but that at some point the potential members decrease.

Monitoring and adjustment: By defining KPIs at this stage, the ECS Academy ensures that membership development can be continuously monitored. If growth diverges from the projections—whether above or below expectations—this will allow for early adjustments in communication, pricing, or membership benefits.

Together, these KPIs provide the context of the ECS Academy’s revenue projections. They make explicit how the reformed membership model can evolve into a stable and predictable financial base, while still allowing flexibility for adjustments if market dynamics require it. These will be revisited and analysed to insure they continue to fit the vision of the ECS Academy and that it remains aligned to the communities needs

4.3 Single Payment for Instructor-led Courses

Single payment refers to payments made by different participants for attending a course on a one-time basis. This includes for example individuals who are not interested in becoming members or wish to test the ECS Academy offers first, thus participating in a specific course offering. Another revenue could come from

organisations that may purchase entire courses (“tailored contract activities”), in which case the participants attending under this arrangement are counted as group-payment or as single-payment users.

The key distinction from membership fees is that single payments are not necessarily recurring and rather unpredictable. They do not originate from existing memberships, but arise solely through the sale of individual courses, whilst specific marketing efforts are necessary (and sometimes costly). As such, they contribute to diversifying the ECS Academy’s revenue base but cannot provide the same reliable foundation for stable, long-term income as memberships do.

4.3.1 KPIS for Instructor-led Courses

For the purpose of the business plan, it was defined as clear KPIs to project the development of single-payment participations over the first four years (table 7). The baseline scenario assumes an average course fee of €200 per participant, with a discounted rate of €100 offered to ensure accessibility for participants with limited resources.

Table 7: KPIs for Participations (Years 1–4)

Year	Single Payment Participants	Single Payment Participants Discounted	Total Participants	Revenue	Revenue Discounted	Revenue Total
0	0	0	0	€ 0	€ 0	€ 0
1	50	15	65	€ 10.000,00	€ 1.500,00	€ 11.500,00
2	75	30	105	€ 15.000,00	€ 3.000,00	€ 18.000,00
3	100	45	145	€ 20.000,00	€ 4.500,00	€ 24.500,00
4	125	60	185	€ 25.000,00	€ 6.000,00	€ 31.000,00

Single-payment KPIs are more variable than membership KPIs, as they depend on demand and attractiveness for specific courses, as well as on the life-cycle of donor money or organisations budget availability (e.g. in economic harsh times, training is less consumed). This may create opportunities for additional revenue in years of high demand, but also underscores the importance of memberships as the stable financial backbone of the model.

Together, these KPIs complement the membership projections and allow for a comprehensive forecast of the ECS Academy’s course delivery requirements and revenue potential.

This combination ensures that the ECS Academy benefits from both stable, predictable revenues through memberships and flexible, demand-driven income from single payments. While the membership model secures a recurring flow of participants and provides planning reliability, the single-payment option expands outreach and allows the ECS Academy to attract learners who prefer one-time engagement without committing to a membership. Together, these two pillars form a balanced and diversified revenue structure that strengthens the ECS Academy’s financial planning and reduces dependence on any single source of income. The aggregated number of participations sold across both models is illustrated in figure 6.

KPI: Development of Participations Sold

Figure 6: KPI: Development of Participations Sold

It is estimated that, on average, each training course will be attended by approximately ten participants, although the actual number may vary from course to course. Based on this assumption, the expected number of courses to be delivered each year can be calculated. If the projected membership numbers for the first year are reached, at least one course per month would need to be offered in order to meet the guaranteed course entitlements included in the membership model. In addition, there will be an unstable additional number of single-payment bookings. To ensure sufficient capacity for this additional demand, the overall number of courses offered should be increased by approximately 50 percent. This precautionary expansion ensures that the ECS Academy can meet both the guaranteed commitments from memberships and the flexible, demand-driven participation generated through single payments.

A detailed breakdown of the financial projections is shown in the section below (4.4) The cost structure includes personnel costs for administration, communication, and IT, as well as expenditures for technical operations and platform maintenance.

4.4 Testing of services

Within the testing phase, several paid online courses were implemented and evaluated in order to assess whether there is sufficient willingness among users to pay for high-quality learning offers in the field of citizen science. In addition, the tests aimed to measure the actual administrative workload, identify the necessary communication activities for participant acquisition and retention together with ECSAs Communication-Team, and determine which of these measures proved most effective. Another important objective was to evaluate the effort involved in participant support and to develop a consistent workflow for course payment and tracking, which could later be transferred into ECSA’s operational structures.

Table 8: List of key selected activities to test ECS Academy services

Date	Format	Trainer(s)	Fee per Participant (€)	Num of Participants	Total Income (€)
<i>Title: Public Participation in Research: A Workshop Series for 2025 MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowship Applicants</i>					
May-September 2025	Online	Pooja Kharuna, Cléa Montenari, Muki, Haklay, Maya Fedeli Anna Berti Suman, Antonella RAdicchi, Uta Wehn, Jaume Piere, James Sprinks,	€20	20	€400
<i>Title: Citizen science training for researchers in Romania</i>					
27 Oct 2025	Online	Muki Haklay, Louise Francis, Gefion Theurmer, Anna Berti Suman		50	€1500
<i>Title: Citizen science training for researchers in Luxembourg</i>					
24 March 2026	Face to face workshop	Muki Haklay		30	€2750
<i>Title: Introduction to citizen science for journalists and science communicators</i>					
15 December 2025	Promotion for online self paced course				Free

Through these tests, the MVP was operationalised and refined in practice. The results provided valuable insights into the functionality and limitations of the current setup and helped establish corresponding workflows within ECSA for coordination, communication, and administration. In parallel, a substantial revision of the technical platform was carried out by the partners. This included the migration of the ECS Academy to a higher-capacity virtual environment, the upgrade of Moodle and its associated components, and the deployment of a new Edwiser-based theme that significantly improved usability and strengthened visual alignment with the citizenscience.eu platform. In addition, course structures and enrolment flows were refined to better support open MOOC formats, and regular iterative adjustments were implemented in response to user needs identified through WP4. Together, these improvements enhanced the overall user experience while remaining fully compatible with the constraints of the MVP.

As a result, the testing phase not only confirmed the basic viability of the ECS Academy model but also generated essential operational knowledge for its sustainable continuation. The findings form the empirical foundation for the further development of the Optimal Technical Environment and support the transition towards the post-project phase, in which ECSA will take over responsibility for maintaining and expanding the ECS Academy. The MVP effort demonstrated an ability to raise income through promotion of training to individuals, and also through working with organisations. This allowed us to navigate several challenges (paypal not accessible in some countries, or minimum and maximum range of bank transfers allowed by different countries/organisations/banks).

4.5 Business plan calculation

The financial model of the ECS Academy as presented here is based on the combination of membership revenues and single-payment participations. To make the business plan robust and verifiable, detailed calculations that merge the two key performance indicators (KPIs) defined earlier were developed. By combining these elements, it becomes possible to estimate the number of courses that will need to be delivered each year to meet the estimated budget necessary to maintain the OTE. The total course volume is derived directly from the sum of included training within the membership tiers and the expected single-payment participations.

On the cost side, the current model only includes variable costs directly linked to the number of trainings delivered. Average costs per training are calculated at €600. This figure is derived from the following parameters: a trainer's daily rate is set at €550, following OECD recommendations. Each training is assumed to last four hours, with an additional eight hours of preparation for the first delivery and two hours of administrative preparation for subsequent deliveries. If we assume that, on average, each training is delivered twice, this results in an estimated average of €600 per training. In practice, however, these costs may vary considerably depending on trainer rates (incl. seniority), course duration, and the extent of preparation required.

Example

Based on these assumptions, in Year 2 the ECS Academy is projected to generate approximately 375 memberships and 75 single-payment participations and 30 single-payment participations discounted. This translates into a total of around 34,5 courses to be delivered (24 through memberships and 10,5 through single payments). With an average of ten participants per course and a fee of €200 per participant, the projected revenue for that year amounts to nearly €90,000, against variable trainer costs of approximately €20,700.

The model is flexible and can easily be adjusted by modifying key assumptions. At present, we assume an average group size of ten participants per course and a standard participant fee of €200. Both of these parameters can be varied to reflect actual market developments. Likewise, membership prices can be recalibrated, which would have a strong influence on the revenue trajectory of the ECS Academy.

List of Key Factors Influencing the Calculation

- Pricing of membership tiers (Basic, Silver, Gold)
- Estimated distribution between regular and discounted memberships
- Estimated number of memberships sold
- Average group size per course (currently 10 participants)
- Participant fee per course (currently €200)
- Estimated number of single-payment participations sold
- Trainer daily rates (currently €550/day)
- Estimated average preparation and delivery time per training
- Estimated average number of times a training is repeated

The resulting calculations (table 9) provide a realistic estimate of the revenues and costs that the ECS Academy can expect under the given assumptions. They show that the combined revenues from memberships and single payments create a solid financial foundation, while variable costs scale proportionally with the number of trainings delivered. In the next step, these figures must be complemented with the ECS Academy's structural costs—such as personnel, technical maintenance, and administration—to complete the full financial picture.

Table 9: Business Plan Calculation

		Year 0 after Transfer of				Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4							
		Price	Amount of Members	Revenue	Participations sold	Amount of Trainings	Additional of Members	Members in Total	Revenue	Participations sold	Amount of Trainings	Additional of Members	Members in Total	Revenue	Participations sold	Amount of Trainings	Additional of Members	Members in Total	Revenue	Participations sold	Amount of Trainings				
Individual	Basic	50,00 €	65	3.250 €	0		10	75	3.750 €	0		10	85	4.250 €	0		5	90	4.500 €	0		5	95	4.750 €	0
	Silver	200,00 €		0 €	0		5	5	1.000 €	5		5	10	2.000 €	10		2	12	2.400 €	12		2	14	2.800 €	14
	Gold	520,00 €		0 €	0		5	5	2.600 €	15		5	10	5.200 €	30		2	12	6.240 €	36		2	14	7.280 €	42
Individual Discounted	Basic	25,00 €	25	625 €	0		10	35	875 €	0		10	45	1.125 €	0		5	50	1.250 €	0		5	55	1.375 €	0
	Silver	100,00 €		0 €	0		5	5	500 €	5		5	10	1.000 €	10		2	12	1.200 €	12		2	14	1.400 €	14
	Gold	260,00 €		0 €	0		5	5	1.300 €	15		5	10	2.600 €	30		2	12	3.120 €	36		2	14	3.640 €	42
Organizations	Basic	200,00 €	15	3.000 €	0		10	25	5.000 €	0		10	35	7.000 €	0		5	40	8.000 €	0		5	45	9.000 €	0
	Silver	540,00 €		0 €	0		5	5	2.700 €	15		5	10	5.400 €	30		2	12	6.480 €	36		2	14	7.560 €	42
	Gold	1.800,00 €		0 €	0		5	5	9.000 €	50		5	10	18.000 €	100		2	12	21.600 €	120		2	14	25.200 €	140
Organizations Discounted	Basic	150,00 €	120	18.000 €	0		10	130	19.500 €	0		10	140	21.000 €	0		5	145	21.750 €	0		5	150	22.500 €	0
	Silver	405,00 €		0 €	0		5	5	2.025 €	15		5	10	4.050 €	30		3	13	5.265 €	39		3	16	6.480 €	48
	Gold	1.350,00 €		0 €	0		0	0	0 €	0		0	0	0 €	0		0	0	0 €	0		0	0	0 €	0
Total			225	24.875 €	0		75	300	48.250 €	120		75	375	71.625 €	240		35	410	81.805 €	291		35	445	91.985 €	342
Total of Trainings by Memberships						0					12					24					29,1				34,2
Total of Single Payment Participation			200,00 €	0	0 €				10.000 €	50				15.000 €	75				20.000 €	100				25.000 €	125
Total of Single Payment Participation Discounted			100,00 €	0	0 €				1.500 €	15				3.000 €	30				4.500 €	45				6.000 €	60
Total of Trainings by Single Payment											6,5					10,5					14,5			18,5	
Total of Trainings											18,5					34,5					43,6			52,7	
Variable Costs (Trainer Payment)		-600,00 €		0 €					-11.100 €					-20.700 €					-26.160 €					-31.620 €	
Total Income Trainings and Memberships				24.875 €					59.750 €					89.625 €					106.305 €					122.985 €	
Total Revenue Trainings and Membership				24.875 €					48.650 €					68.925 €					80.145 €					91.365 €	

4.5.1. Yearly Structural Costs for the ECS Academy

The structural costs are recurring expenditures that ensure the ECS Academy can operate effectively and maintain a stable technical and administrative environment. Structural costs cover personnel, technical infrastructure, operational expenses, and quality assurance. Unlike variable costs, they are largely independent of the number of courses offered and therefore represent the fixed foundation of the business plan. The table below (table 10) summarises the main structural cost items, their roles and explanations, calculations for full-time equivalents (FTE) and costs under both the Minimal Viable Product (MVP) and the Optimal Technical Environment (OTE).

Table 10: Structural yearly Costs for the ECS Academy

Cost Item	Role/Task/Explanation	Category	Pay Scale	FTE MVP	FTE OTE	Costs MVP	Costs OTE
1. Personnel costs							
Academy Coordinator	Product management, course integration, customer support, acquisition of new courses, curation.	personnel cost	TVL 14 Stufe 3	10%	50%	9.000,00 €	45.500,00 €
Communications	Social media promotion, website updates, outreach to potential users..	personnel cost	TVL 13 Stufe 3	10%	50%	8.400,00 €	42.000,00 €
Technical Maintenance	Support for Moodle and plugins, updates, troubleshooting.	personnel cost	TVL 13 Stufe 3	15%	50%	13.000,00 €	42.000,00 €
2. Tech infrastructure							
Technical Maintenance	Maintaining existing Moodle setup; €9,600 annually estimated for plugins.	technical infr.	-			300,00 €	1.000,00 €
3. Operational costs							
Office rent and utilities	Workstations, electricity, internet, heating - in-kind by host organisation.	operational cost	-			2.400,00 €	2.400,00 €
IT equipment and licenses	Hardware/software, cloud backups, security (~€750/year/person).	operational cost	-			300,00€	2.775,00 €
Administrative, HR, legal	Contracting, salary admin, tax/legal review (~20% of personnel costs estimated).	operational cost	-			6.080,00 €	25.900,00 €
4. Other							
Training, QA, User Tests	Honoraria for testers, surveys, adjustments (~ 5-10% of technical dev. costs).	-	-				5.000,00 €
Contingency Reserve	Reserve of 10% of total budget items 1.-4.	-	-				16.657,5€

Cost Item	Role/Task/Explanation	Category	Pay Scale	FTE MVP	FTE OTE	Costs MVP	Costs OTE
Total						39.480,00€	183.,232.5€

This structural cost framework demonstrates that the ECS Academy's sustainability depends not only on revenues and trainer payments, but also on securing stable funding for its organisational backbone. These costs will differ significantly depending on whether the ECS Academy operates at the MVP level or within the OTE.

4.5.2 Investment required

The ideal environment where we can respond to the predicted demand for courses, resources and other services is the OTE, for which we are not able to secure the costs as it is significantly higher than what we expect to gain as revenue. In order to solve this we estimate an initial investment of approximately 200.000€. This investment would support the development of the optimal technical environment, helping ECSA to reduce the operational burden of maintaining the ECS Academy and to strengthen its capacity to generate revenue for both maintaining and further developing the Academy in line with the Citizen Science Competency Framework and the needs of the community.

Table 11 - Preliminary plan of the use of investment money in a period of one year

Cost Item	Role/Task/Explanation	Pay Scale	FTE MVP	Costs
1. Personnel costs (Personnel costs calculated based on the German public sector collective agreement for the federal states (TV-L), using 2026 salary levels as reference values.)				
Developer	Creation of technical space tailored to all the academies needs including a pre defined list of services	TVL 13 Stufe 3	75%	62.000,00 €
Academy Coordinator	Communication with the community to identify needs beyond what is described here. Liaise with the developer and communications team. Development of updated business plan and timeline. Administration of courses and resources. Coordination of ECS Academy pedagogical content and user needs. Work with management on the development of restructured membership model.	TVL 14 Stufe 3	50%	45.000,00 €
Communications	Create tailored communication plans to raise awareness about the ECS Academy and its services	TVL 13 Stufe 3	50%	42.000,00 €
2. Tech infrastructure				
No costs as it would be hosted directly by ECSA				
3. Operational cost				
Office rent and utilities	Workstations, electricity, internet, heating - in-kind by host organisation.			2400,00 €
IT equipment and licenses	Hardware/software, cloud backups, security, server space			3000,00 €

Cost Item	Role/Task/Explanation	Pay Scale	FTE MVP	Costs
Administrative, HR, legal	Contracting, salary admin, tax/legal review (~20% of personnel costs estimated, excluding Admin personnel).			29.800,00 €
4. Other				
Training, QA, User Tests	Honoraria for testers, surveys, adjustments (= 5–10% of technical dev. costs).			5.000,00 €
Contingency Reserve	Reserve of 10% of total budget items 1.-4.			18.920,00 €
Total				208,120.00 €

The table above shows the predicted time investment towards the development of a system which would subsequently require less personnel cost to maintain.

In sum, the OTE is not only a technical upgrade but a strategic investment. While structural costs are significantly higher than under the MVP, we overcome this by creating our own infrastructure and thus unlock the ECS Academy's full potential, ensure its financial sustainability, and position ECSA as the key European hub for citizen science training and capacity building.

This investment is essential for creating a self-sustaining structure that secures the ECS Academy's long-term viability. Beyond the immediate needs of the ECS Academy, it can also serve as a blueprint for other initiatives, enabling future European projects to build their own academies on a proven and reliable model. In this way, the business plan does not only ensure the sustainability of ECS but contributes to the broader vision of establishing a network of European academies.

The business model thus creates a sustainable future through a balanced combination of mixed funding, membership income, single-payment revenues, and continued collaboration with partner organisations.

5. Handover of the ECS Academy to ECSA

Outlook

Figure 7: Outlook for the future of the ECS Academy

Based on both the MVP and the OTE described above and some initial testing of the different services the ECS Academy can offer, **we created a handover plan containing a mix of elements from both models and some new services not considered at the time.** The OTE remains our main goal towards a long term sustainability of the ECS Academy where an investment is crucial (figure 7).

In the next sections we describe how ECSA will maintain and expand the ECS Academy once the ECS project ends given its current capacity and its long term plan.

5.2 Handover timeline with adapted service offerings

This handover will go in 3 phases:

Phase 1: In line with the principles of open science the majority of the content within the ECS Academy will remain free for every user under a creative commons licensing. Fees will be charged for instructor-led courses where content is tailored to particular target groups needs or when the course was designed for self-learning and the instructor provides additional value, this will also include summative evaluation and providing a certificate to participants beyond the auto-generated badges. Course authors are always the primary instructor to deliver this service but alternatives may be chosen in particular situations, all to be defined between ECSA and course authors in a standard MoU (currently being developed). Furthermore, specialised events, such as summer schools and other training events will be organised with other partners to continue promoting the ECS Academy as a central learning hub for citizen science. For these events participant fees will be calculated based on the event costs including an adjusted percentage that should go towards the sustainability of the ECS Academy.

Courses will be also delivered upon request - for example, an invitation from a national funder to deliver a training to researchers, or an institution approaching ECSA to provide training. In these cases, the model will follow closely the instructor-led courses above. The ECS Academy will keep a 25% overhead of all charges made under its services that will towards maintenance and slow progression towards the OTE.

To kick-off the handover, 2 members of ECSA HQ team will work together to fulfil the role of the ECS Academy coordinator whilst the ECSA communication team will incorporate the ECS Academy as part of their day to day activities and will expand and implement a communication plan for the ECS Academy (section 5.3 - Communication plan). An ECS Academy working group will be created to support the HQ team in the continued growth of the ECS Academy in a way that is aligned with the communities needs. During this phase services described in table 1 will be free of charge whilst a structure for the charging of these can be implemented.

Phase 2: During this phase we will expand the catalogue of services the ECS Academy can offer at a fee. Instructor-led courses and specialised events will continue to be offered the same way.

The ECS Academy coordinator and the ECS Academy WG will establish an expanded approach that foresees that partners and collaborators can either make use of individual services (e.g. course hosting, participant management, or payment handling) or opt for bundled service packages tailored to their needs. This flexible model allows various stakeholders to benefit from the ECS Academy’s infrastructure without duplicating efforts, while at the same time generating revenue streams to cover operational costs. Some elements of support are considered mandatory for all who use the ECS Academy in the future. This includes hosting and troubleshooting on the platform as well as administration and enrolment support to ensure smooth operations and safeguard the ECS Academy’s standards of quality (table 12). Prices for the different services can be based on a daily rate of €450, pegged at the EU payment for experts.

During this phase, and depending on the governance model and agreement for the Citizen Science Competency Framework (CitSciComp), the ECS Academy might be able to start offering courses that are recognised for accreditation and compliance with CitSciComp. To achieve that, ECSA will establish a compliance and scrutiny committee that evaluates courses and applications by candidates. Candidates will need to complete a given number of courses from the catalogue, and pay a certain fee per module (about €250) or per a bundle of training (€800). At the end of which, they can deliver a portfolio that will be evaluated by the committee and they will be recognised at the appropriate competency level in CitSciComp.

Table 12: Staff capacity estimation for different services

Service	Task	Responsibility	Time
Support for hosting	Integrating courses in a scorm-package (universal format) directly and hosting them on the platform	Technical Maintenance	2h/course
Support in self-administration and enrolment	Supporting the teacher in the self-administration of their course	Academy Coordinator	1h/course
Support for content development	Partners who prepare their own course materials using the ECS Academy template can receive technical and administrative support. This includes advice on structuring the course, building resources, and uploading content to Moodle	Academy Coordinator	1h of a course is ca.1-2 days of support

Taking care of the entire content development process	If desired, the Academy can manage the full development of course content. This includes drafting and uploading text, examples, exercises, and resources	Academy Coordinator	1h of a course is ca. 5 days of support
Support for technical development / introduction to Moodle	For partners who already have course content but lack technical expertise, the Academy provides assistance with uploading and integrating the material into Moodle.	Academy Coordinator	Courses ready (not in scorm-packages): 2-3 days / course
Support for pedagogical design	Course providers requesting assistance in aligning their content with effective pedagogical standards or the learning paths of ECSA Academy.	Academy Coordinator	1 day per course
Support for facilitation	If a partner wishes to run an instructor-led course, the Academy can help identify and connect with trainers within the ECSA network.	Academy Coordinator	The level of support depends on the course design and trainer fees, making this service subject to individual negotiation.
Support in communication and dissemination	For raising visibility, the communication team can assist with promoting courses through Academy and ECSA channels.	Communication Team	This service starts at two hours of staff time per course and can be scaled depending on needs.
Support in financial management	For instructor-led courses, the Academy can take care of administrative financial processes such as participant invoicing and fee management.	Academy Coordinator	Roughly 2 hours per course
Support for hosting resources on Zenodo	The Academy can upload and maintain resources on Zenodo to ensure open access and long-term availability.	Academy Coordinator	Takes approximately 30 minutes per resource, depending on complexity

These time estimations can be converted to PMs when courses are developed as part of projects that ECSA is part of, or charged as a fee independently. Through these optional services, the ECS Academy ensures that any partner using its infrastructure can rely on professional support while at the same time contributing financially to the sustainability of the platform. ECSA remains open to special partnerships including all of these services to anyone, for which the contact point will be the ECS Academy coordinator.

Phase 3: This is where we start working towards the OTE described in the next section. This phase can go in 2 ways. Without the previously described investment we will start implementing selected features of the OTE as current capacity allows it. This will depend on generated revenue and also existing capacity at the ECSA HQ team.

Alternatively, a one-time investment of €200,000 will enable the development of the Optimal Technical Environment through a tailored technical space and create the structural foundation for long-term sustainability.

The benefits of the OTE (and thus of the investment) are multifaceted:

- **Scalability:** The ECS Academy will be able to significantly expand the number of courses offered, thereby scaling the reach and impact of citizen science across Europe.
- **Sustainable Revenue:** By enabling a broader and more professional course offering, the ECS Academy can generate substantial revenues and operate sustainably within a mixed funding model.
- **Lower operational costs:** The new technical environment will create automated process and reduce a lot of manual work for things such as invoicing, registrations and certification among others.
- **Stronger Memberships:** Attractive membership models with integrated course benefits provide strong incentives for individuals and organisations to join and remain engaged with ECSA, creating a long-term bond within the citizen science community.
- **Meaningful Use of Resources:** The investment allows the ECS Academy to establish stable human resources and invest in highly qualified personnel, thereby guaranteeing further development in alignment with the CitSci Comp. It also encourages more educators and trainers to contribute to the ECS Academy's activities.
- **Enhanced User Experience:** The new technical setup will create a seamless environment for registration, payment, and communication. It can also serve as a blueprint for other educational initiatives across Europe that aim to secure sustainability but lack the resources to build such an advanced infrastructure
- **Less Fragmentation:** With this increased support, the ECS Academy will be able to forge synergies with other learning hubs and offer a more comprehensive course catalogue, aligned with the CitSci Comp. This will support investments from the EC to be used more effectively towards new content that is needed instead of duplicating work.

This investment is therefore not only essential for the ECS Academy's internal development but also represents a broader opportunity to strengthen citizen science capacity building across Europe.

5.3 Communication Plan

A robust communication plan is a central component of any business model and fundamental strategic dimension that directly contributes to value creation. The dimensions "Channels" and "Customer Relationships" are core elements identified in the value proposition canvas (section 3.2 - Value proposition analysis). They ensure that the value proposition of the ECS Academy reaches its defined target groups, builds trust, and ultimately translates into active participation, memberships, and sustainable revenues.

In the context of the ECS Academy, communication plays a dual role: it aims to engage existing members and learners while simultaneously attracting new audiences to the platform and its offerings. This chapter outlines a phased communication strategy that aligns with the development stages of the ECS Academy and supports its long-term sustainability. This is a structure which will be expanded in partnership with ECSAs communication team as part of the handover process.

Communication action 1: Building the ECS Academy

During the 1st stage, communication focuses on the internal and external positioning of the ECS Academy. Internally, this includes clear messaging around the ECS Academy's mission, structure, and value to the ECSA network. Externally, the priority lies in creating visibility for the ECS Academy as a credible and high-quality provider of citizen science training.

Key measures include:

- Announcing the ECS Academy through all available channels (ECSA, including all its networks and working groups, ECS, and partner organisations)
- Developing a strong and coherent visual identity for all communication materials, aligned with the ECS Academy's design and embedded within ECSAs infrastructure such as newsletter, mailing list and social media channels
- Highlighting flagship courses and pilot offerings to demonstrate early value and credibility

This phase is essential for creating initial trust, building recognition, and setting the foundation for all subsequent engagement.

ECSA will introduce the ECS Academy and selected courses and events at both member specific events and events open to the community to onboard newcomers to the platform and advertise new features.

Communication action 2: Showcase of new services

New services will be developed and tested following ECS's co-design approach, thus with different levels of support from the community. The engagement of specific audiences, the online component of this process and the organisation of related events will include a communication plan aligned with materials developed in action 1.

Once a service is finalised and is ready to be released, a tailored programme of social media campaigns and events will be developed by the ECS Academy coordinator and the communications team to introduce it to current and potential new users. These will take different forms depending on target audiences and the specific of the service and will always include a hands-on component to increase long term use of services being developed.

This will be organised alongside the actions described in action 1 that will continue throughout the ECS Academy's lifetime.

Communication Action 3a: Membership Transition and Community Engagement

Once the technical infrastructure of the Optimal Technical Environment (OTE) is in place and the ECS Academy is fully operational, communication will focus on supporting a possible transition towards a revised membership model, subject to the relevant ECSA governance processes and approval by the General Assembly.

ECSA currently has 293 members in total, consisting of 184 individual members, 93 non-profit organisational members, and 16 for-profit organisational members. Existing ECSA members will be invited to transition into the revised membership structure integrating ECS Academy services. To support this transition, they may be offered limited-time incentives, such as a three-month free trial period for selected membership levels. This approach lowers the entry barrier and allows members to directly experience the added value of the ECS Academy's integrated services.

Key messages in this phase include:

- Transparent explanation of the new membership structure and its benefits
- Emphasis on the inclusion of training entitlements within memberships
- Personalised communication (e.g. direct e-mails) to members to support their renewal
- Testimonials from early adopters and satisfied learners

- Framing the ECS Academy as a collective investment into the future of citizen science

Simultaneously, all new organisations within the identified target group segments will be addressed through focused marketing campaigns and personalised outreach, clearly communicating the long-term benefits of active organisational membership.

The goal is to ensure a smooth and inclusive transition with minimal loss of current members, while deepening engagement and signalling the added institutional value of the new ECS Academy structure.

Communication Action 3b: Dual Track – Growing the Base and Marketing Courses

After the membership transition, communication must operate on two parallel tracks:

1. Recruitment of New Members: Strategic outreach to target groups, multipliers, and networks to expand the ECS Academy's user base. This includes:

- Targeted campaigns in sectors such as research, education, public engagement, museums, and policymaking
- Participation in conferences and events
- Co-marketing with partners and alliances

2. Marketing of Individual Courses: Instructor-led courses (ILCo) are available for single-payment purchase and must be actively promoted. This requires:

- Campaigns tailored to the specific topic and audience of each course
- Highlighting the relevance, quality, and impact of the learning opportunity
- Leveraging instructors' own networks for visibility
- Using social media, newsletters, and platform integration to boost reach

The key is to align each message with the interests of the specific audience and to use the appropriate channels and formats for outreach.

Sustaining Communication

To ensure long-term success, the ECS Academy aims to institutionalise its communication activities. Processes described in both action 1 and 2 will continue and will also include an expanded strategy for maintaining engagement from ongoing members together with a communication and a long-term acquisition strategy:

- **Member Communication:** Regular newsletters, updates on new courses, community spotlights, and opportunities for feedback and co-creation are essential for retaining members and fostering a sense of belonging.
- **Acquisition Strategy:** Communication efforts must not stop after the initial launch. A sustainable model requires continuous outreach to new potential members and learners, supported by strategic partnerships and visibility in the field.
- **Course Promotion:** The marketing of single courses must be aligned with the topic and its audience. For example, a course on biodiversity data may be promoted through environmental NGOs, while a course on citizen science in schools might be shared through education networks.

5.4 Roadmap Towards Sustainability

At the outset of this work, the ambition was clear: to develop a fully functional and self-sustaining product that would safeguard the project's outcomes beyond the lifetime of the grant. This foundation has been successfully established through strategic planning and collaborative efforts, positioning the Academy for continued growth and development under ECSA's stewardship.

The business plan and fee structures described in previous sections outline how the ECS Academy can generate stable revenues through a combination of memberships and single-payment courses, complemented by a flexible service model for partners. Together with ECSA's commitment to assume legal and operational responsibility, this creates the institutional conditions for viability and sustainability. At the same time, the roadmap acknowledges the need for interim steps and measures: maintaining the MVP, incrementally building up services, and actively seeking funding for the technical upgrade.

The ECS Academy as it is today already demonstrates significant value as a learning hub, with proven success in engaging members and attracting participants through diverse learning opportunities. This success reflects ECSA's strategic vision and the collective efforts of consortium partners, particularly those engaged in T6.4 and WP4. The creation of an optimal technical environment will only further enhance this towards a more robust and active learning hub. Such an environment can be achieved swiftly with targeted investment offering in return scalability, sustainable revenues, stronger membership engagement, substantially and a less fragmented ecosystem with improved user experience.

The ECS Academy represents more than just a learning platform, it embodies ECSA's broader strategic vision of supporting the citizen science community's growth. Its success is intrinsically linked to ECSA's organizational success, making it a catalyst for the Association's future development.

Annexes

Annex 1 - Identification of exploitable resources

Data analysed

- The web-platform citizenscience.eu
- Reports from the first project period:
 - D2.1 Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report
 - D2.2 Engagement and community-building plan
 - D2.4 EU-Citizen.Science Sustainability Plan
 - D7.3 Final Impact Assessment Report
 - D7.1. Evaluation & Impact Framework
 - D7.2 Interim Impact Assessment Report
- Other materials, including:
 - ECSA_Ten_principles_of_CS_German.pdf
 - ECS_D6.1_Communication and Dissemination Plan_20221130.pdf

Interviews conducted (January-March 2023)

- ECSA Dorte Riemenschneider, Claudia Fabó Cartas
- ZSI Barbara Kieslinger, Stefanie Schuerz
- Stickydot Marzia Mazzonetto, Florence Gignac
- SfC Rosa Arias, Carla Perucca Iannitelli
- Ibercivis Jorge Barba
- CSIC Amalia Cárdenas, Ana Álvarez
- UP Muki Haklay, Cléa Montanari
- MfN Marius Oesterheld

Interview Guideline

The semi structured interviews were guided by the following questions:

Internal Analysis

- Stakeholders
 - User groups – who uses the platform, where do the users come from, what are they looking for?
 - Partners – who is involved in the platform as a partner?
 - External service providers – what services are contributed externally?
 - Funding – who paid what for the platform?
- Content
 - What services and what content already exist for what user groups?
- Primary Activities – how does ... work?
 - Content production – producing the services, writing blog entries, recording organisation's entries
 - Marketing / Networking
 - User communication / support

- Secondary Activities – how does ... work?
 - Server / Hosting
 - Web design
 - Content Management
 - Coordination / Project team
- Costs
 - What is the platform's cost structure?
 - What costs is the business model supposed to cover?

External Analysis

- Political
 - What meaning does citizen science have on the political agenda of the EU / member states?
- Economical
 - Market: What national competitors in the EU exist?
 - Market: What international competitors exist?
 - Finance: What fields / industries are already funding citizen science?
 - Finance: What fields / industries could be interested in funding citizen science?
- Technological
 - What technological improvements / changes in media use can influence the platform?
- Legal
 - What legal aspects are relevant for the platform (licensing, liability, Intellectual Property Rights, privacy rights, usage rights etc.)

Annex 2 - SWOT-Analysis (February 2023)

Strengths

- The eu-citizen.science webpage is well regarded as an authority for citizen science in Europe among key stakeholders.
- The eu-citizen.science platform has been successful in procuring European R&D grants in various projects promoting and implementing citizen science.
- ECSA is recognised and has a strong network in academia and scientific institutions.
- ECSA has an increasing network in the European national citizen science networks.
- The associated organisations to ECSA are linked to an existing membership base.
- The ECS project is funded by Horizon Europe and has funds to the further development of eu-citizen.science platform and the creation of related services
- The topic of citizen science is gaining weight in European R&D projects and from the policy perspective (e.g. CS-Pact for R&I in Europe) it's not considered as an isolated topic any more – a mainstreaming effect.

Weaknesses

- Citizen science players often lack the sustainable resourcing required to live up to its potential.
- The eu-citizen.science platform as well as ECSA have temporary funding and is generally faced with weak and low funding streams, both at EU and country level, while other sectors (e.g. private) are still unexplored and underdeveloped.
- Without the Horizon Europe funding, ECSA has limited personnel capacity to provide services. Any new service offering will likely induce the need to hire specialised personnel.
- ECSA has limited personnel capacity to manage the overhead induced by operating an income model.

- In any model, ECSA will likely have to hire (administrative/specialised) staff.
- The ECSA membership formula is based on voluntary participation, it lacks a clear and more structured governance model.
- ECSA doesn't own data, intellectual properties or any other type of goods that could be monetised – and needs to be careful in how to balance monetisation in relation to open science policies. Services are thus the only option for generating an income.
- The website traffic on <https://eu-citizen.science/> is not sufficient to utilise target ads via Google's AdSense as an income stream, and this would also have a negative impact on the overall value of the site for its user base, as it would be detrimental to usability and would make less credible
- The eu-citizen.science platform does entail fixed costs, such as maintenance and hosting, which need financing after the end of the EU funding period in order to be sustainable.
- The eu-citizen.science platform is currently not set up to offer services and handle financial transactions. This would need to be developed first.

Opportunities

- The funding provided by Horizon Europe offers a unique chance to implement one-off activities associated with creating an income stream.
- The ECS project currently funded by Horizon Europe Coordination and support action includes many partners from across Europe that are well-established in the citizen science community. These partners are instrumental in validating potential income streams and in promoting newly created offers by the ECS project.
- Citizen science is an evolving field of practice. It is promoted by the European Union within its wider open science agenda to develop the scientific position of Europe. This creates a need for expertise and opportunities for the provision of services in citizen science.
- There are numerous target groups that have a demand for expertise in citizen science. These include scientific institutions and universities, graduate centres of universities, scientists and citizen science practitioners, Horizon Europe practitioners that need/want to include citizen science in their Horizon Europe project, as well as private industry. Income streams could be generated by offerings catering to this demand.
- The currently running ECS project includes the ECS Academy which offers a chance to establish a service structure to cater to the above-mentioned demand.
- Furthermore, European national ministries and funding agencies are increasingly supporting citizen science in line with the European agenda. This provides a conducive environment for the creation of national platforms for citizen science where there are none yet, and include them in policy development and/or decision-making. Income streams could be generated by offerings catering to this demand.
- Although the Grant Agreement envisages a more permanent income stream in the sustainability plan, having another temporary funding source could be another path of securing the future of eu-citizen.science at least for some time.
- The membership format at ECSA can be developed further and made more attractive and beneficiary for potential interested target groups.

Threats

- National platforms for promoting citizen science could be competitors that offer similar services as the eu-citizen.science platform.
- The ECS project is dependent on external funding. Once this funding concludes, the eu-citizen.science platform will have difficulties to be continued.

- Any income stream will have to be decided upon and created in the period of the current funding. This makes a timely decision necessary.
- The ECS project consortium includes many members with potentially divergent interests. This can make the decision on an income model difficult.
- All financial resources available by funding of the ECS project by the EU, are planned for specific activities. Any currently not planned activities needed to create prerequisites for an income stream will lead to change requests, and potentially the suspension of other planned activities.
- External competition from international CS-actors outside of Europe having more resources and experience may impact the newly developed business and exploitation plan/model of ECSA.
- Legal risks such as privacy and usage rights in addition to new disruptive technologies (e.g. AI) can have an impact on the success of the eu-citizen.science platform.

Annex 3 - Long List of potential Ideas (June 2023)

With reference to the results of the SWOT analysis and the data collected from the interviews conducted during the exploration phase, the findings were summarised in a long list of ideas for potential services or products that would add value to the basic services provided by ECSA and could therefore be offered for a fee, thus contributing to the goal of financial sustainability.

European Citizen Science Academy

One very relevant proposal was to monetise certain offers of the European Citizen Science (ECS) Academy. The ECS Academy was considered to have key-potential in developing services and generating possible revenues. However, it should also be noted that large parts of the ECS Academy will continue to be available to everyone free of charge, following open science principles and values inherent to citizen science. Also, for legal reasons, training which is already available and certain future training must be made accessible to everyone free of charge, as it is not necessarily permissible to monetise content which has been provided for free to eu-citizen.science, following the well-known public good principle. This is not the case if live trainers or mentors are involved, when monetisation is possible at least to honour the expertise and time of the trainers involved. Possible options for income generation for such offers are tailored training, accompanied learning, coaching, training material, certificates, and supervision by the trainers.

Dedicated Web Sections for National Citizen Science Networks and Associations

The presence of EU countries on the platform could be renewed, with each country receiving its own websection on the platform. Each section could normally have two forms: Either (1) a linking of the national platform or (2) an overview of the national offerings with hyperlinks for all countries that do not yet have their own national platform. For the latter, a new presence could be created: A curated national section with content in the national language that appears like a designated national platform but is integrated into the eu-citizen.science web platform. The aim of the curated section is to create a low-cost offer for national entities to establish their own digital presence without having to set up their own online platform. National entities would need to raise funds at the national level to finance such a dedicated web section. The costs of the suggested solution could be far lower than the costs involved in providing their own platform. These funds could be divided into two areas. On the one hand, the national entity finances local staff which is responsible for the national content. However, part of the funding goes to ECSA, which uses the money to provide the technical infrastructure and staff to supervise and guide all curated sections. In any of these cases it is required to keep in mind that different legislation can lead to a higher administrative burden.

Advertising

Tools and software which could be used in the context of citizen science are already being promoted on the platform. In the future, services that are not free of charge could be advertised for a fee, while offers given free of charge could be further advertised without a fee. Another option for advertising could be the integration of Google Ads, although it is important to reiterate that the SWOT analysis showed that the traffic on the platform is currently not high enough in this respect. Also legal and ethical considerations have to be made when it could come to a cooperation with a private company. In addition, advertisement could be obtained from both public and private entities, i.e. the establishment of mutually beneficial partnerships. However, ethical considerations regarding private advertising as well as for the overall value of the site for the community will likely cause severe limitations.

Paid Content and Services on the Platform

The platform could be used to provide paid content. Some partners have already suggested possible options for paid content during their interviews with Nordlicht. The options entail curated content and tailor-made services and outsourcing of tasks. The paid content could be made accessible per piece or via a membership fee, which could for example be linked to membership of ECSA, thus enhancing the value of becoming a full member of ECSA. The target group for paid products is not always entirely known and depends on the specific contents and services. The community of citizen science practitioners is probably rather small and likely not very solvent. The investments to launch this idea are relatively high, which is why revenues would first have to be generated to cover those investment costs before staff or other overheads can be financed.

Temporary and Structural Funding

Although the Grant Agreement of the ECS project aims for a permanent source of revenue in the Sustainability Plan, having another temporary source of funding following the end of ECS could be a way to secure the future of eu-citizen.science at least for some time. This would entail for the hosting organisation of eu-citizen.science, ECSA, to procure grants that allow for a further financing of citizenscience.eu activities and services. In addition, a more structural solution could come from both the EU (e.g. a permanent operating grant) and national sources (e.g. Germany as host country of ECSA), which could provide structural support measures for ECSA and/or the eu-citizen.science platform. There is a risk that any funding applications (both temporary and structural) are not successful. This option is considered as a high risk for the whole project due to a constant uncertainty. If successful, the business model may create new positions and contribute to new content and involvement. There is without great hesitation a consensus among the partners to continue the platform and related cooperation.

Consulting Services for Industries

Some large companies are using methodology which might resemble a citizen science approach. They involve employees and/or citizens to collect data which they can use for business purposes. An example of such collaboration are "living labs", which have so far been primarily used to engage customers. A business model could be developed where industry is advised on how to set up living labs and how to engage customers and/or citizens in data collection keeping in mind the spirit of citizen science. Such projects can also be successful for industry contract research, especially within the health sector. However, there are already companies dedicated to this form of consulting and it is unrealistic that ECSA can be sufficiently successful as a non-profit organisation. In addition, presumably, this type of consulting is not uniquely consistent with the values of ECSA

Annex 4 - Detailed Explanation of Business Model Canvas

The original Business Model Canvas consists of the following nine categories: Customer Segments, Value Propositions, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure. These categories provide a generic framework for describing how a business creates, delivers, and captures value. However, in the context of the ECS project, we had to adapt these categories to better reflect the nature of our use case – which is not a traditional profit-driven enterprise, but a public-good-oriented service structure embedded in a European research and innovation context.

We therefore restructured the business model framework using categories that are more relevant to our goals, stakeholders, and operational environment. These adapted categories are outlined in the following section, each with a short explanation of its content:

Key Activities - Services

WP4 had already drawn up a detailed list of services at this point. In a further workshop on December 4, these services were condensed and evaluated.

Key Partners – Personnel Resources

The “Key partners” in this business model are made up of two groups. On the one hand, there is the network of partners who support each other in terms of content. On the other hand, the partners who will help with the infrastructural (IT infrastructure) implementation of the ECS Academy. The former play a role above all in the context of “channels” and communication, the latter are defined more precisely in relation to the distribution plan. This is why it was decided to not use the category of “Key Partners” from the original framework but to work with the category of “Personnel Resources”.

Key Resources – Governance

Key Resources are not a central element of our business model. Instead we here use the category of “Governance” to describe the structure the ECS Academy is built on and provide the best framework for its execution.

It has become clear that the ECS Academy’s development should already be supported by ECSA during 2025 to ensure a smooth handover at the end of the project. The hiring of an Academy-Coordinator at an early stage, ideally during the current ECS project implementation, was seen as a prerequisite, including calculating the personnel costs (in the category of “Personnel Resources”) for the ECS Academy and working out a governance structure between UP (WP4) and ECSA.

Value Proposition

The value proposition was developed as part of the project meeting in Barcelona in July 2023 and is the prerequisite for this business model canvas.

Customer Relationships and Channels – Communication and Distribution

Instead of having two categories, i.e. “Customer Relationships” and “Channels”, the partner’s thoughts led to define the categories “Communication” and “Distribution”. “Communication” refers to the need for a communication and marketing concept, which must be developed in collaboration with WP6.

“Distribution” refers to the need for a distribution concept, which includes

- Front and Back-End / IT-Infrastructure for the ECS Academy
- Data management
- Payment Infrastructure

Customer Segments – Target Groups

Customer Segments are the Target Groups for the ECS Academy and will be defined in the chapter below.

Cost Structure and Revenue Streams

These categories are identical to the original business model canvas and have been addressed later in the process.

Annex 5 - Structured Feedback Survey

The aim of the survey was to obtain feedback from people and institutions involved in the project about their opinions on the two ideas for possible services and products. The ECS Academy and web platform were analysed again on the basis of the report "Strategic Positioning of ECS" and criticism, additional thoughts and comments should be made. The survey was conducted using the online tool Lamapol. Participation was possible for approximately six weeks, until 9th of July at 12:00. All project partners received the link and information about the survey on May 25th 2024, and two reminders were sent to the same group asking them to participate. The evaluation serves to provide an overview of the results and ideas, but also forms part of the basis for deciding which idea should be prioritised further in a business plan. In fact all the results of the survey are valuable for the further development of the business plan. Moreover, the open response sections in particular are a source of ideas and perspectives that will enrich the way forward. In conclusion, participants were clearly in favour of prioritising the ECS Academy. The ECS Academy was perceived as more suitable and feasible than platforms and in the direct vote, the vast majority of participants would prioritise the ECS Academy as an idea.

Structure of the Survey

In principle, participation in the survey was only possible if an email address and the associated organisation, institution or facility were provided. After this initial question, the focus was initially on the fundamental feasibility of the two ideas for generating an income stream for ECSA: ECS Academy and Platforms. The participants were asked to give their assessment in 5 steps from '1 - very high' to '5 - very low'. In addition, there was the possibility to indicate in a text field whether the participants could think of organisations or individuals who could particularly benefit from the respective offer.

The next questions targeted Ethical and Legal implications of the ECS Academy and National Platforms. Indeed Non-commercial projects, especially at European Union level, have a high ethical standard. Undoubtedly this is particularly important when it comes to generating monetary income. It helps to collect different thoughts from different areas. For this reason, participants were asked to express possible ethical or legal concerns in an open response format.

In addition to the specific questions, it was important for the authors to open up a space for questions or comments that were not addressed so far. Furthermore, being able to utilise the broad knowledge and experience of a wide range of partners and receive criticism from them, which in itself helps the project to progress, was and is a great strength of working together. For this reason, all participants were able to make comments and critics in an open text-answer format.

The last question in the survey was undoubtedly the most important and most direct. In a single choice question, the participants were able to state which of the potential ideas they would favour (if they could decide on their own).

The individual questions:

- *How do you rate the feasibility of the ECS Academy generating income stream? (scale)*
- *How do you rate the feasibility of the web platforms for generating income streams? (scale)*
- *Do you have organisations or individuals in mind that could value such an offer? (open)*
- *What ethical concerns could arise when implementing the ECS Academy/Platforms in a business plan? (open)*
- *What legal concerns could arise when implementing the ECS Academy/Platforms in a business plan? (open)*
- *Is there anything which hasn't been addressed so far, which you would like to point out? (open)*
- *Finally - if it's up to you, and you would have to decide - which of the two potential ideas should be prioritized for an implementation during the current ECS project? (single choice)*

Results and Evaluation

The survey was open for 8 weeks and several reminders were sent to the consortium and its members by email. However, shortly after the survey was closed, the evaluation began. The survey was started a total of 30 times, 11 participants completed the survey in full.

As shown in the diagram, most participants identified themselves as partners from the consortium. Representatives from the following institutions took part in the survey: FGC, NILU, Stickydot, CSIC, Universidade Lusófona, ZSI, Learning Planet Institute, ECSA, Ibercivis, Museum für Naturkunde.

Web platform

The general feasibility of the web platform in generating an income stream was rated as medium to rather high by the participants. On a scale of 1 (very high) to 5 (very low), most participants (5) gave it a 3. One person rated the feasibility as very high, 4 participants gave it a 2. In terms of organisations or individuals that could benefit from the web platforms, the open responses focused on smaller EU countries that either do not yet have a CS community or do not yet have a website (Ireland, Romania). Italy was mentioned twice. Indeed the CS Association there has only recently established itself (as of May 2024) and could benefit in particular in the eyes of the participants. Legal or ethical concerns that could arise if the platforms were to be implemented primarily

related to the security of personal data. It was also noted that the language used for platforms should be taken into account. In fact in some countries, there are several official languages. Furthermore, each country should also provide all information in English so that people and institutions from all EU countries have the opportunity to use it. Maintaining a balance between regional languages and the more widely used languages was therefore a key concern in the responses. In addition to the ethical question of considering the significance of different languages, the legal focus was on dealing with intellectual property. Undoubtedly this question is closely linked to how the platform should be managed, who is responsible for content and who can make decisions in the event of disputes. In fact the question of governance is of great importance, if web platforms should be prioritised.

ECS Academy and comparison to web platforms

The feasibility of the ECS Academy to create an income stream was rated as high by a majority of the participants. 7 voted considered the feasibility as 2 (scale 1 “very high” – 5 “very low”). Overall, the feasibility of the ECS Academy was detected as higher than the feasibility of web platforms. In the open section arising the question of which organisations and individuals could value from the offer of the ECS Academy a variety of future profiteers was identified.

The questions addressing potential ethical concerns focused on ethical issues regarding the accessibility of the ECS Academy. It was emphasised that all services must also be accessible to those with limited financial resources. "Inclusivity" as a keyword not only for people who are already in the Citizen Science Network, but also for those who want to join. In addition, the handling and security of collected (personal) data was seen as the main concern or challenge.

Concerns or comments on legal issues centred on the fact that national and regional legislation must be considered, especially when it comes to the ECS Academy issuing certificates. Who is authorised to train whom and what consequences (qualifications, etc.) can arise from this that create added value? Furthermore, questions of personal rights and privacy (including data protection) also play a role in the considerations of the remarks of the participants.

However, the main point in the comments on legal implications possible arising is the governance of the ECS Academy. Which person or institution can speak on behalf of the ECS Academy must be clarified. Especially if the ECS Academy wants to operate and develop as a legal entity. Internal governance structures should, if possible, be considered from the outset and form a basic structure for the next steps. All of these considerations will play a role in the possible creation of a business plan once the decision in favour of or against the ECS Academy has been made. Moreover, in this case the open answer section of the ECS Academy will be analysed in-depth.

Finally, the participants were given a direct choice as to which idea they would favour (if it were only up to them). This question was very clearly in favour of the ECS Academy. 10 participants voted for the ECS Academy, only once voted for prioritising the web platforms.